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**ECOLOGICALLY SAFE SECONDARY METABOLITES OF PLANTS
OF THE GENUS ARTEMISIA AND JURINEA AND PROSPECTS FOR
THEIR PRACTICAL USE.**

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Abstract: This article presents the results of phytochemical study and practical application as anthelmintic, antimalarial, antitumor, antiatherosclerotic agents in medicine and biological tests of growth-regulating, mutagenic, antiparasitic and insecticidal activity in cotton growing, sericulture, rice growing, as well as against termites of a number of environmentally safe individual sesquiterpene lactones and the sum of lactones isolated from the aerial parts of plants of the genus *Artemisia* and *Jurinea* of the Asteraceae family growing in Uzbekistan.

Key words: terpenoid, sesquiterpene lactone, sum of lactones, cotton, silkworm, rice, termite.

Аннотация: В данной статье приводятся результаты фитохимического изучения и практического применения в качестве антигельминтных, антималярийных, противоопухолевых, антиатеросклеротических средств в медицине и биологических испытаний рострегулирующей, мутагенной, противопаразитарной и инсектицидной активности в хлопководстве,

шелководстве, рисоводстве, а также против термитов ряда экологически безопасных индивидуальных сесквитерпеновых лактонов и суммы лактонов выделенных из надземных частей растений рода *Artemisia* и *Jurinea* семейства Asteraceae произрастающих в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: терпеноид, сесквитерпеновый лактон, сумма лактонов, хлопчатник, шелкопряд, рис, термит.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda o'suvchi Asteraceae oilasiga mansub *Artemisia* va *Jurinea* turi o'simliklarini yer ustki qismini fitokimyoviy o'rganish natijasida ajratib olingan ekologik xavfsiz individual va seskviterpen laktonlar yig'idisini tibbiyot amaliyotida gelmintlarga, bezgak, saraton, sklerozga qarshi vosita sifatida qo'llanilishi va paxtachilik, pillachilik, sholichilikda hamda termitlarga qarshi o'stiruvchi, mutagenli, antiparazitar, insektitsidli faolligi bo'yicha biologik sinov natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: terpenoid, seskviterpen lakton, laktonlar yig'indisi, g'o'za, pilla, sholi, termit.

Introduction. The flora of Uzbekistan is very diverse and rich. Of the 8,000 thousand species

growing in Central Asia, 4,500 plant species are represented in the country.

To create and introduce new effective medicines and chemical plant protection products, it is necessary to expand the development of methods for obtaining biologically active compounds from wild and medicinal plants of the flora of Uzbekistan. Currently, in medicine and agriculture, synthetic drugs are mainly used, which are quite toxic and pollute the environment, however drugs created on the basis of plant materials are almost non-toxic, but have a wide range of biological effects, are environmentally friendly to humans, animals and the environment.

In recent decades, among a wide range of secondary metabolites of plant origin, the class of terpenoids, including sesquiterpene lactones, has attracted particular interest from researchers. They attract the attention of researchers around the world,

not only for their interesting chemical and structural features, but mainly for their wide range of biological activities, including antimalarial, antimicrobial, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antifeedant, antiviral, anthelmintic, antifungal, etc. [1-3]. Many of the biological activities are attributed to the presence of an α -methylene- γ -lactone group in their molecule, which reacts via Michael addition with free sulfhydryl or amino groups in proteins and alkylates them. Due to the fact that most sesquiterpene γ -lactones are thermolabile, less volatile compounds, they do not contain specific chromophores in the molecule and are sensitive to acidic and basic environments. Another problematic aspect is the complex composition of plant extracts, which makes the separation of individual compounds difficult. Therefore, their isolation, identification and quantification represent a very labor-intensive task for the researcher.

Although sesquiterpene lactones are present in approximately 16 plant families, they predominate in the Asteraceae family, and in the flora of Uzbekistan, plants of this family are very widely represented both in the diversity of species and in the cover they occupy.

This article presents literature and our own data on the study of sesquiterpene lactones from plants of the genus *Artemisia* and *Jurinea*.

Research methods. To isolate sesquiterpene lactones, aerial parts of plants were extracted five times with chloroform with further purification of the extracts from ballast substances by precipitation. The resulting and purified number of lactones was separated by chromatography on a column filled with silica gel and sequentially eluted according to polarity with organic solvents. The isolated individual compounds were repeatedly recrystallized and IR, UV, mass and PMR spectra were recorded.

When studying the mutagenic effect of the polar sum of *Artemisia absinthium* (preparation "PRP") on cotton, mutant lines were obtained. For field testing, seeds of various cotton varieties were soaked in the drug at concentrations (2.0; 1.5; 1.0; 0.5%) and then sown.

To examine the growth stimulating activity of the lactones we have isolated on rice seeds, the following technique was used. A weighed portion of the test substance was dissolved in a small amount of ethyl alcohol and then diluted with water to a volume in a ratio of 1:10,000. Rice seeds were individually immersed for 24 hours in the resulting solution of each terpenoid, and the seeds were also soaked in water (control). The yield was determined by dry weight and the results were compared with the control.

For preliminary analysis of plants for alkaloid content, crushed aerial parts of plants were moistened with a 10% aqueous solution of soda and then extracted with chloroform. The condensed chloroform extract was treated with a 10% sulfuric acid solution. A solution of soda was added to the sulfuric acid solution until the solution became alkaline and then extracted with chloroform. The resulting chloroform extract was concentrated and a qualitative reaction was carried out with Dragendorff's reagent.

To determine the optimal concentration of antitermite activity of sesquiterpene lactones, they were tested using the following method:

A sample of each test lactone (0.5 g) was dissolved in a small amount of acetone and the volume was adjusted to 50 ml by adding distilled water. Then 1 ml of the resulting 1.0% solution of the drug was diluted to 100 ml. and a 0.01% solution was obtained, which was then diluted to the required concentrations for testing.

Results and discussions. Among the sesquiterpene γ -lactones from the above genera that we have isolated, compounds with antitumor, antiviral, insecticidal, antibacterial, biostimulating and mutagenic effects were identified.

The genus *Artemisia* (wormwood) is one of the largest in the Asteraceae family and is represented in the world flora by about 500 species, of which more than 120 species grow in Central Asia and 82 species in Uzbekistan [4].

According to ongoing phytochemical studies, it has been established that wormwood mainly produces two classes of secondary metabolites, terpenoids and phenolic compounds in major quantities. Biological and pharmacological tests have

revealed that from the point of view of medicine and agriculture, the sesquiterpene γ -lactones produced by wormwood, which have a variety of biological actions, are of particular interest [5,6]. Of the more than 5000 sesquiterpene lactones, about 700 are isolated from members of the genus *Artemisia* and in these plants the most common types of sesquiterpene lactones are guaianolides, eudesmanolides and germacranolides.

As a result of pharmacological studies, a number of sesquiterpene lactones have found widespread use in medical practice for the treatment of various diseases.

The first sesquiterpene lactone, α -santonin (Figure 1), isolated from *Artemisia cina* and also produced by many *Artemisia* species, has been widely used in the last century as an anthelmintic that removes parasitic worms from the body by killing or stunning them. Due to serious side effects and the development of many safer anthelmintic drugs, α -santonin has largely fallen out of use. The sesquiterpene lactone tauremisin, isolated from *Artemisia taurica* (tauric wormwood), is used in medicine as a cardiogenic and central nervous system tonic, as well as for mental and physical fatigue. Arsubin lactone, isolated from *Artemisia sublessingiana*, has a similar effect like tauremisin. In China, an antimalarial drug was developed based on the sesquiterpene lactone artemisinin (Fig. 1), which is isolated from *Artemisia annua* L [7]. In 2001, the World Health Organization recommended the use of artemisinin to control malaria. Chinese researcher Tu Y.Y. received the Nobel Prize in 2015 for this discovery of new methods of treating malaria. Currently, arteannuin B (Fig.1) and a number of artemisinin derivatives (dihydroartemisinin, dihydroartemisinin methyl and ethyl esters, dihydroartemisinin succinate) are used as effective antimalarial and antitumor agents, and their production has been established in China, India, Vietnam, and Switzerland. The antitumor drug "Arglabin", which is a water-soluble hydrochloride of the dimethylamino derivative arglabin, was developed in Kazakhstan; it is based on the sesquiterpene lactone arglabin (Fig. 1), which is isolated from the endemic plant of Kazakhstan *Artemisia glabella* Kar. EtKir. It is registered as an antitumor drug for the treatment of various types and stages of breast, lung and liver

cancer in Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation [8]. Based on the guaianolide leucomysine (Fig. 1), produced by the aerial part of *Artemisia leucodes*, the drug “Oligvon” was created, which is recommended by the Pharmacological Committee of Uzbekistan as an anti-atherosclerotic agent and is more active than the well-known drugs “Anginin” (Japan), “Productin” (Hungary), “Privalagin” (USA) [9].

Figure 1. Biologically active sesquiterpene lactones

The preparations “PRP” and “SPG” created on the basis of the sum of wormwood lactones, as well as some individual lactones, showed high biostimulating and mutagenic activity in cotton growing, sericulture and rice growing [10-14].

In cotton growing, chemical mutagens and ionizing radiation are mainly used in the selection of source material. When using mutagens of plant origin, it is possible to obtain valuable starting material for breeding purposes in a short time.

The amount of extractive substances of *Artemisia absinthium* as a stimulating mutagenic factor was tested on cotton seeds. The following were analyzed: seed germination, plant survival and the degree of development of traits characterizing productivity. In experimental variants at concentrations of 1.0 and 0.5%, there is a

pronounced stimulation, in particular, in the accumulation of fruit organs on the bush, an increase in the weight of raw cotton per plant, due to an increase in the number and weight of bolls.

This drug was used as a modifier to relieve depression during irradiation of cotton seeds. The varieties C-6524 and C-9070 were taken for the study; gamma rays of Co60 and the drug "PRP" at a concentration of 2 and 1% were used as mutagenic factors. The control consisted of non-irradiated seeds simply soaked in water and the second control - simply irradiated seeds.

As a result of research, a number of promising mutant lines and varieties have been obtained. Of these, two varieties have passed state tests and are superior to the well-known variety S-6524 in terms of economically valuable traits. From the polar sum of wormwood, a new water-soluble sesquiterpene lactone of the guayan type with mutagenic activity was isolated by chromatographic separation on a column filled with silica gel, its chemical structure was established and, apparently, it is the active principle of this drug [15].

The influence of the extractive amount of wormwood (WAG) on the productive and reproductive properties of silkworms was also studied. To determine the biostimulating effect, mulberry leaves were treated in various concentrations with an aqueous solution of the sum of sesquiterpene lactones until they were completely wetted. The caterpillars were fed the treated leaves from the first day of the fifth instar, daily, until the cocoons curled. It was found that the use of aqueous solutions (0.10 - 0.25%) leads to an increase in the productivity of the silkworm, and at the same time the viability of caterpillars and the average weight of cocoons increases by 15%, the yield of grains increases, and silk production increases by 3.1 %.

The fight against particularly dangerous infectious diseases of the silkworm (nosematosis and nuclear polyhedrosis) is possible through a targeted search for new modern preventive agents from the group of herbal preparations.

As a result of the studies, it was found that the “ALEU” product, which is the sum of lactones isolated from *Artemisia leucodes*, has biological activity that can inhibit the transition of the latent jaundice virus to an active state, i.e. slow down the development of the disease. Toxicological studies have revealed that this product is environmentally friendly to humans, animals and the environment.

As a result of treating grains with this preparation, viability increases by 3.4%, and viability increases by 5.8 - 8.0%. Accordingly, such caterpillars curl larger cocoons, with a mass 0.11-0.15 g higher than caterpillars emerging from untreated grain. The yield of cocoons from one box of greens increases by 3.6-4.1 kg.

The antiviral activity against the latent nuclear polyhedrosis virus on silkworm grains of aqueous solutions of alkaline hydrolysis products of the sesquiterpene lactones leucomysin, austricin, arteannuin B, and α -santonin was also studied (Fig. 1). The results of the experiment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.**Influence of products of alkaline hydrolysis of sesquiterpene lactones on the viability of the grain and the viability of the silkworm**

Lacto-nov hydrolysis products	Leucomysin (1)	Austricin on (2)	Arteannuin B (3)	Santonin (4)	Water (control)
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Solution concentration (%)	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	-	
Yield of caterpillars from treated grain (revitalization of grain)	95.8	96.2	96.6	94.8	95.0	96.1	97.6	95.8	95.5	
Total % of death from JAP virus induction	27.1	30.7	32.8	23.8	28.9	35.5	30.2	32.0	43.4	
Increased viability compared to control (%)	16.3	12.7	10.6	19.6	14..5	7.9	13.2	11..3	-	

The table data shows an increase in the vitality of grain in most experimental variants by 0.3-2.1% compared to the control variant. In addition, in all experimental variants, the death of caterpillars from the induction of nuclear polyhedrosis, relative to the control, decreases and the viability of the silkworm increases after the induction of the nuclear polyhedrosis virus from 7.9% - 19.6%.

Thus, the tests conducted indicate a positive effect of the products of alkaline hydrolysis of the sesquiterpene lactones leukomysin, austricin, arteannuin B and α -santonin on the viability of grena and the viability of the silkworm to the disease nuclear polyhedrosis, which depends on the concentration of the solution and the structure of the studied lactones.

We examined the antinosema activity of the sum of mono- and sesquiterpenoids isolated by extraction from plants *A. tenuisecta* (ATEN), *Artemisia annua* (AANN). The resulting amounts of terpenoids were used to treat greens infected with nosematosis that had undergone a wintering period in concentrations of 0.5% and 1.0% of each option. The grena was kept in the prepared solutions for two hours, then dried, placed in a thermostat for incubation, and on the third day the caterpillars emerged from the grena, a count was taken based on the viability of the grena.

Table 2

Infection of caterpillars with nosematosis after treatment with a sum of sesquiterpene lactones

	Symbol of the product and concentration, %	Infestation of revived caterpillars,%	Reduced infection compared to control	
			abs. %	rel. %
	ATEN 0.5	4,5	3,6	44,4
	ATEN 1.0	1,8	6,3	77,8
	AANN 0.5	3,2	4,9	60,5
	AANN 1.0	2,4	5,7	70,4
	Control (water)	8,1	-	-

From the analysis of the results obtained, presented in Table 2, it follows that treatment of nosematosis-infected grenade with solutions of extracts of biologically active substances reduced the infestation of emerging caterpillars compared to the control by 3.6-6.3% absolute, or by 44.4-77.8% relative percentage. Among them, the agents with the code names ATEN in 1.0% concentration and AANN in 1.0% concentration turned out to be the most effective, having a high antinosema effect. The caterpillars emerging from the treated grena were microscopically examined separately.

The growth-regulating activity of a number of terpenoids isolated by us from *Artemisia tenuisecta* and *A. absinthium* on rice seeds was also considered. As the results showed, the most active growth regulators were α -santonin and artabine, which significantly increased rice yield by an average of 11 - 12.5% [16-19].

Artabine

Plants of the genus *Jurinea* Cass. (Asteraceae) are widespread and there are about 300 species in the world flora, 98 species in Central Asia, 34 species of which, grow in Uzbekistan [4]. They have long been used in folk medicine to treat various ailments such as colic, puerperal fever, gout, rheumatism, fever, and extracts and some individual lactones have been found to have antibacterial, antimicrobial, fungicidal and insecticidal properties. Previously, plants of this genus were considered alkaloid-bearing, but the results of our studies of some species of these plants showed that these plants do not contain alkaloids. It is known that sesquiterpene lactones containing an exocyclic methylene group conjugated to the lactone ring easily form adducts with ammonia and secondary amines, which can lead to erroneous results for the presence of alkaloids in plants that contain sesquiterpene lactones. Therefore, preliminary data on the isolation and presence of alkaloids in the *Jurinea* species we have studied are erroneous and the isolated alkaloids are not native, but secondary products of the addition of ammonia to sesquiterpene lactones. Phytochemical studies have established that plants of the genus *Jurinea* mainly produce sesquiterpene lactones of two structural types: germacrane and guiana, and all of them have a nonlinear structure, that is, the lactone cycle is located at C-6, C-7 carbon atoms, examples of which are the structures of salonitenolide, salonitolide, knitsin, shachimardon isolated from *Jurinea* shachimardanica and *J. kokanica* [20].

In recent years, the widespread occurrence of two types of termites is a serious problem in Central Asia: the Turkestan termite (*Anacanthotermes turkestanicus* Jacobs) and the large Transcaspian termite (*A. Ahngerianus* Jacobs), which are dangerous pests and cause enormous damage to historical cultural monuments,

buildings, structures, warehouses and strategic objects. The results of many years of testing have shown that synthetic drugs used against termites do not give serious tangible results, and apparently, the main disadvantage of these drugs is their short-term action and toxicity. Recent studies have shown that the most promising long-acting intestinal termicidal preparations are sesquiterpenoids isolated from plants of the Asteraceae family. American scientists isolated the sesquiterpene lactone knicin from *Centaurea maculosa*, and the sesquiterpene ketone vulgarone B from *Artemisia douglasiana*, which showed high antitermite activity. Other authors found that a mixture of vulgarone B and knitsin, due to a synergistic effect at low concentrations, led to 96-100% death of termites [21,22].

The results of laboratory and field tests revealed that a number of germacranolides have high intestinal termicidal activity with prolonged action. The sesquiterpene lactones knicin and salonitenolide, isolated from the aerial parts of the plants *Jurinea shachimardanica* and *J.kokanica*, which in a mixture (3:1) at low concentrations (0.001%-0.005%) lead to 100% death of termites on 6-10 days of application (table 3) [23,24].

Table 3

Termiticidal activity of knicnin and salonitenolide

Knicin-salonitenolide (3:1).	Number of termites	Observation day																			
		1-st		2-nd		3-rd		4-th		5-th		6-th		7-th		8-th		9-th		10-th	
		p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w	p	w
0,001	20		20		20	-	20	-	20	5	15	-	15	7	8	7	1	1	0		0
0,002	20		20	2	18	-	18	2	16	-	16	1	15	9	6	1	5	5	0		0
0,003	20		20	4	16	6	10	-	10	7	3	2	1	1	0						0
0,005	20		20	2	18	3	15	-	15	7	8	-	8	6	2	2	0				0
Control	20		20		20		20	3	17	2	15	1	14	-	14	1	4	-	14	-	14

Note: p – dead termites; g – live termites.

Conclusion. Based on the above data, we can conclude that the phytochemical study of sesquiterpene lactones and total extracts of plants of the genus *Artemisia* and *Jurinea* of the Asteraceae family will lead to the creation of highly effective medicines and pesticides, the rational use of local plant raw materials, solving environmental problems, creating promising new varieties, as well as increasing yield and productivity of agricultural production.

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